

IMPACT OF PUBLIC INVESTMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This paper emphasizes on the important role that public investment can play in coming years for realizing government policy goals of economic development (poverty reduction, climate change mitigation, as well as responding to forthcoming demographic trend) particularly in intensified urbanization. It also visualizes the empirical record whether big infrastructure and public capital drives have succeeded in accelerating economic development as big long-lasting drives in public capital spending, were arguably clear for making exogenous policy decisions. On average, the picture would indicate weak association between development and public investment in short run period impact but in long run, bond becomes stronger. It argues against the importance of long term productivity effects, as these are triggered by the completed investments (which take several years) and not by the mere spending on the investments

Keywords: Public Investment, Economic Development, Macroeconomic Effect, Economic Growth And Cost-Benefit Analysis.

I-INTRODUCTION

Public investment is public expenditure that adds to the public physical capital stock which supports the delivery of key public services, connects citizens and firms to economic opportunities, and can serve as an important catalyst for economic growth. Public investment by federal, state, and local governments build nation's capital stock by devoting resources to the basic physical infrastructure (such as roads, bridges, rail lines, airports, and water distribution), innovative activity (basic research), green investments (clean power sources and weatherization), and education (both primary and advanced, as well as job training) that leads to higher productivity and/or higher living standards. While private actors also invest in these areas, they do so to a much smaller degree, in part because the gains from public investment accrue not just to those undertaking the investment, but to a wide range of people and businesses.

After three decades of decline, public investment has begun to recover as a share of GDP in emerging markets (EMs) and low income developing countries (LIDCs), but remains at historic low in advanced economies (AEs). The increase in public investment in EMs and LIDCs has led to some convergence between richer and poorer countries in the quality of and access to social infrastructure (e.g., schools and hospitals), and, to a lesser extent, economic infrastructure (e.g., roads and electricity). However, the economic and social impact of public investment critically depends on its efficiency.

In recent years, some debate has centered around increasing public investment to provide a near-term boost to the job market, based on research showing that infrastructure investment is about the most efficient fiscal support one can provide to a depressed economy. But there is also an enormous amount of economic evidence demonstrating that public investment is a significant long-run driver of productivity growth—and hence growth in average living standards. Both theoretical and empirical studies have

underscored the positive relationship between high-quality public infrastructure and economy-wide productivity. Against the background of a steady decline in public investment as a share of GDP in advanced economies, evidence of infrastructure bottlenecks in emerging and developing economies, and the sluggish global economic recovery, many have called for ramping up public investment to raise long-run economic growth and development.

II-LITERATURE REVIEW

The role of public investment in the process of economic growth and development has been the subject of enquiry of a growing body of both theoretical and empirical literature. The starting point for both strands of literature is the notion that actions taken by governments have considerable effect on macroeconomic performance. For example, the level of public investment may affect both private investment and the long-term rate of growth. The fact that public investment is largely non-excludable and non rival in consumption suggests spillover effects, and this is emphasized by the endogenous growth models.

Most empirical studies of the effect of public infrastructure on economic development have estimated its indirect effects by relating various assures of public capital to measures of economic development. **Mera(1975)** provides the most comprehensive test of the effect of public investment on economic growth for the U.S. He hypothesized that growth of economic activity is determined primarily by the growth of public infrastructure and technical progress. While **Khan and Reinhart (1990) and Khan and Kumar (1997)** suggested that private capital formation is more productive, and hence more growth enhancing than public investment. This neither necessarily imply that all forms of public investment are equally productive, nor that investment in public infrastructure is necessarily better for growth than other forms of public Expenditures.

Khan (1996) explored the relative importance of public and private investment in promoting economic growth for a large group of developing countries. The results of the study showed that private and public investment have a differential impact on economic growth and development, with private investment having a much larger impact than public investment. Also, significant regional variations are found in terms of the effects of public and private investment. **Devarajan, Swaroop, and Zou (1996)** focused on the composition of public expenditure and showed that whereas current public expenditure had positive and significant growth effects, the effect of capital component of public expenditure on per-capita growth is negative.

IMF, 2004; Scandizzo and Sanguinetti, (2009), the evidence seems to be mixed on the impact of aggregate public investment rates – broadly defined – on growth, with some studies finding little relationship between public investment rates and per capita gross domestic product (GDP) growth. This is not surprising for a number of reasons. An important part of public investment outlays support the broad functions of government (provision of social services, redistribution, maintenance of law and order, administration), which only indirectly feed into the factors influencing productivity growth. Much public investment is of a “lumpy” nature, focused on infrastructure that has its impact on productivity only over a long period of time. Moreover, as already noted, the data on public investment has numerous deficiencies, excluding the contribution of spending on education and health, and overstating the level of investment (by virtue of ignoring any measure of the depreciation of public capital).

III-OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This paper will explore the relationship between public investment, growth and development factor with the aim of providing an overall view of existing theories, evidence and methods, and of looking at possible ways to provide better guidance to policy-makers in the use of available techniques and information to set priorities for public investment.

The paper is not meant as an exhaustive review of all existing material, but simply as a summary of the main contributions and findings whose main objective to provide decision makers with a set of general rules-of-thumb that are likely to help them improve the macroeconomic returns of public investment.

IV-Public Investment – Macro Economic Effects

I have examined five channels through which public investment can affect economic growth and economic development namely: **complementing private capital, crowding-in private investment, increased market integration, increased aggregate demand, and increased national savings.**

1. *Public capital and private capital are complementary:*

Most discussions on the effect of public investment on economic growth begin with the assumption that public capital and private capital are complementary to each other. This is justified on the ground that public capital and private capital are made up of quite different things, with public capital consisting mainly of public goods (e.g. roads, electricity supply) and private capital consisting of private goods (e.g. buildings, machinery). In this case, the aggregate production function for an economy can be explained in the form of following equation:

$$Y = A \cdot f(K, G, N, L) \quad (1)$$

where Y is aggregate output, K is private capital (human and/or physical), G is public capital, N is natural resources, L is the labour force, and A is the level of technology, or total-factor productivity. An increase in the public capital stock raises aggregate output. It also raises the productivity of all other factors of production, including labour. If labour markets are competitive, and labour supply is inelastic, an increase in the productivity of labour leads to an increase in real wages.

When public capital and private capital are complementary in this way, an increase in public investment will raise a country's rate of growth, at least up to a point. To illustrate, assume that Equation (1) can be approximated by a Cobb Douglas function of the form:

$$y = A \cdot k^\alpha g^\beta \quad (2)$$

where $y = Y/L$ is output per worker, $k = K/L$ is private capital per worker, and $g = G/L$ is public capital per worker, and the parameters α and β represent the elasticity of aggregate output with respect to private and public capital respectively. Assuming that the rate of private saving is unaffected by the return to private investment. The long-run or 'steady-state' level of output per worker (y^*) is as given below:

$$y^* = A^{1/\gamma} \left(\frac{s_p}{\delta_k} \right)^{\alpha/\gamma} \left(\frac{s_g}{\delta_g} \right)^{\beta/\gamma} \quad (3)$$

Where sp is the share of private investment in national income, sg is the share of public investment in national income, δ_k and δ_g are the rates of depreciation of private and public capital respectively, and $\gamma=1-\alpha-\beta$. The prediction is that, in the long run, countries with higher rates of public investment will have higher levels of output per worker (*ceteris paribus*). In the short- to medium-run, as they approach their long-run steady-state level of output per worker, countries with higher rates of public investment will have higher rates of economic growth (again, *ceteris paribus*).

2. *Crowding-in private investment :*

Additional considerations arise when the rate of private saving is flexible, and adjusts in response to changes in the returns to private investment. When public and private capital are complementary, public investment raises the marginal productivity of private capital. This raises the returns to private investment and (if private savings are flexible) the amount of private investment. This 'crowding-in' of private investment in turn increases the rate of economic growth.

However, although public investment is almost certain to crowd in private investment when starting from a low level, it is unlikely to do so at all levels. This is because increases in public investment have a successively smaller positive impact on the returns to private investment, while the taxes required to finance them have a constant negative impact.

At some stage, therefore, it is inevitable that increased public investment will 'crowd-out' private investment. Nevertheless, many developing countries are in likelihood a long way from this point, given their low levels of tax revenues relative to GDP.

3. *Market integration :*

In 'new economic geography' models, improvements in domestic transport and communications infrastructure can have significant effects on growth. There are two reasons for this. The first is that, by lowering transport costs, firms' profits are raised, as are (depending on the characteristics of the labor market) the wages paid to labor. This generates a one-off boost to average income. The second is that, by driving a cumulative process by which labor and other resources move to a small number of core regions and/or cities in which (because of increasing returns) levels of labor productivity are higher. An acceleration in a country's rate of growth is caused, which may well persist over several years, if not decades.

4. *Increased aggregate demand:*

In Keynesian models of the economy, public investment affects the level of national income through its effect on aggregate demand. Such models assume that, because of inflexible wages and/or prices, economies sometimes operate at less than full employment. In such cases, an increase in public investment would have an immediate positive impact on the level of national income, followed by a successively smaller positive impact in a limited number of subsequent years. Alternatively, for economies with some positive underlying rate of growth, a rise in public investment would initially cause growth to accelerate, followed by a gradual deceleration back to the underlying rate. There are, in fact, many examples of such growth accelerations in developing countries in recent decades, although it is not known what proportion can be attributed to increases in public investment.

5. *Increased national savings:*

It is also possible that public investment will increase economic growth simply by raising the rate of national savings. Put simply, a government can, in some circumstances, increase the share of national income that is saved by taxing consumption and investing the revenues this generates. For this particular effect to occur, the rate of private saving must not fall significantly if public investment reduces the returns to private investment. However, whether a government can raise national savings in this way is, of course, contested.

V-Public Investment- Evidences

In this section, I summarize the most recent empirical evidence regarding the various channels through which public investment affects poverty. Such evidence is important for two reasons. First, it provides empirical tests of the hypotheses derived from the theories outlined in Section III. Second, it allows policy-makers to make more informed choices, ex-ante, about the optimal level and inter-sectoral allocation of public investment .

1. *Effects of public investment on economic growth :*

Several studies have looked at the impact of public investment on economic growth. One of the earliest examples was **Barro (1991):He found that the average share of public investment in GDP had a positive, but statistically insignificant, impact on economic growth over the period 1960–85.** This was followed by a study by **Easterly and Rebelo (1993)**, which extended the analysis in two directions. First, they included investment by public enterprises as well as that by central government; and secondly, they distinguished between public investments in different sectors. In contrast with Barro (1991), they found that public investment by central government had a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth. They also found that, of the different sectors, investment in transport and communications had a particularly large, and statistically significant, effect on economic growth. More recent studies of the effects of public expenditure on growth have included **Aschauer (2000) and Milbourne et al. (2003)**: Both tested the predictions of a neo-classical growth model in which public capital is a complementary to private capital, and found that public investment had a positive and statistically significant impact on economic growth. Of the different sectors, investments in transport, communications and education have the largest impact on growth (the effects of investments in agriculture, health, housing and industry are not statistically significant).

2. *Effects of public investment on poverty :*

Some recent studies have estimated the effect of public expenditure, including public investment expenditure, on poverty. Using cross-country data, **Gomanee et al. (2003) and Mosley et al. (2004)** had estimated the effects of government expenditure in different sectors on the US\$1-a-day poverty headcount, holding the level of GDP per capita constant. **They found that higher government expenditure on education, agriculture, and housing and amenities (water, sanitation and social security) all have a negative and statistically significant impact on poverty, presumably by shifting the distribution of income in a pro-poor direction, since the level of aggregate income is held constant in their regressions.**

Other studies have used cross-state data, particularly in India where state-level data are high-quality and

stretch far back in time. Fan et al. (1999), for example, estimated the effect of public expenditure on levels of rural poverty across Indian states, distinguishing between expenditure on rural education, targeted rural development, public health, irrigation, power generation, agricultural R&D, and rural roads. They found that agricultural R&D, rural roads, rural education and targeted rural development expenditure all had negative and statistically significant effects on rural poverty. Of these, spending on agricultural R&D and rural roads has by far the largest impacts on both growth and poverty reduction. Fan et al. (2002) conducted a similar analysis of the effects of public expenditure on rural poverty across Chinese provinces, distinguishing between expenditure on rural education, targeted poverty alleviation, telecommunications, irrigation, power generation, agricultural R&D, and rural roads. They found that spending on rural education has the largest impact on poverty, followed by spending on agricultural R&D and then by spending on rural roads. More recent studies on India, China, Uganda and Thailand include Fan et al. (2004a).

3. Effects of public capital on inequality :

I end this section by summarizing the results of some recent studies which have looked more directly at the effect of different types of public capital, as opposed to public expenditure on public capital, on poverty or inequality. **Calderon and Serven (2004)** estimated the effect of their indices of infrastructure quantity and quality on inequality, as measured by the Gini coefficient. **They found that both indices have a negative and statistically significant effect on the level of inequality.** I have been unable to locate any similar studies, although this work is likely to stimulate further work on this issue. Some studies, however, have estimated the effect of infrastructure on poverty using micro-econometric evidence. **Deininger and Okidi (2003)**, for example, found that households in Uganda that were connected to an electricity network in 1992 experienced much higher rates of income growth over the period 1992–99 than households that were not.

4. Summary

This section shows that there is a large and increasing body of evidence on the impact of public capital and public investment on productivity, economic growth, inequality and poverty. This represents an important resource from which policy-makers can draw facts in order to make better public investment decisions. This evidence shows that public capital is generally productive, in the sense that it boosts output at the sectoral or national level, in addition to any direct welfare benefits provided to households. Often, the boost to productivity from an increase in public capital is significantly larger than that arising from an equivalent increase in private capital. The evidence also shows that public investment expenditure is associated with greater poverty reduction, at least in those countries with sufficiently detailed and reliable data on government expenditure and poverty across states or regions to allow conclusions to be drawn. The main limitation with the existing evidence, however, is that there are still relatively few studies of the impact of public capital or investment in specific individual countries.

VI- Method of measuring public investment

In this section, I look at methods used to assess whether a specific public investment project can be justified, in other words, techniques of project appraisal. However, while discussing useful ways to assist policy-makers, the importance of making comparisons among investment opportunities in different

sectors cannot be overestimated in order to be able to identify an optimal portfolio of public investment for reducing poverty and achieving other social goals.

The standard technique for assessing ex -ante the merits of a proposed public investment project is **cost-benefit analysis (CBA)**. The basic principle of CBA is simple and well known. It involves identifying all the people likely to be affected by a public project, and then measuring the net impact of the project on each person – the benefits minus the costs – in terms of current money income. A project is said to be justified if the weighted sum of all the net benefits is greater than zero. The weights reflect the government’s judgment regarding the relative importance to be attached to the project’s measured net benefits going to different members of society, including those who have not yet been born.

Two fundamental questions in CBA are: a) how can all the different costs and benefits of a project be converted into current monetary terms; and b) what weights should be used when adding up the net gains or losses of different members of society. We consider briefly each of these issues in turn.

1. Measuring net benefits in monetary terms:

The monetary impact of changes in the quantity or quality of additional public capital used by firms is given by the marginal impact of public capital on firm profits. Given time-series or cross-sectional information on farm profits and levels of public capital, as well as various other factors likely to affect farm profits, this can be estimated econometrically. For recent estimates for irrigation investments in Vietnam, see **van de Walle and Gunewardena (2001)**.

The monetary impact of changes in the quantity or quality of final goods and services consumed by households is given by households’ marginal monetary valuations of the goods being provided. There are three main ways of calculating these valuations: the contingent valuation approach, the travel cost method, and the hedonic pricing method. All these approaches have been used extensively in measuring the benefits of ‘environmental’ public goods and services (e.g. national parks, air pollution, and noise pollution).

2. Weighting costs and benefits:

When public investment raises the rate of growth, it increases the levels of income and consumption that can be attained in future. Converting these benefits into current value terms requires a decision as to the level of discount rate to use. My argument is that, because of technological progress, incomes tend to grow over time . Combined with the assumption of diminishing marginal returns to income, this implies that net benefits accruing to future generations should be given less weight than those accruing to current generations. In the absence of any technological progress, however, there are no strong normative or ethical grounds for weighting net benefits accruing to future generations any differently to current generations.

When public investments also have distributional effects, CBA requires a decision as to whether to weigh differently the net benefits accruing to different households and, if so, how. There has been a long and important literature on this issue. On the one hand, it is argued that the most efficient way for governments to achieve their distributional objectives is through the use of taxes and transfers. The implication is that the net benefits of public investment projects going to different people need not be weighted differently. This view was originally associated with the assumption that ‘lump-sum’ taxes and transfers – defined as those which have no effect on the behavior of donors or recipients – were possible.

On the other hand, it is argued that governments cannot achieve all the distributional objectives through the tax and transfer system, and that opportunities for ‘lump-sum’ taxes and transfers are limited (e.g.

Sen, 1972; Weisbrod, 1972; and van de Walle, 2000). Combined with the assumption of diminishing marginal returns to income, the implication is that net benefits of public investment projects should be weighted according to the level of income of the person to whom they accrue, with greater weight being placed on net benefits going to individuals with lower incomes. This was advocated, for example, in the study for the World Bank by Squire and van der Tak (1975). However, there is no clear guidance as to what these weights should be, except in terms of it being a normative matter that should be decided by a government in consultation with citizens.

3. Using CBA to assess poverty impacts:

A special weighting system would be one which places zero weight on net benefits going to households above income poverty line, and a weight of one on net benefits going to households below that line. In this case, the CBA would show the impact of the project on the welfare of the poor, measured in monetary terms, which would correspond quite closely with the change in the poverty gap measurement of income poverty (assuming the CBA was carried out well).

However, many critics would question whether such a weighting system can be justified and/or is ever likely to be used in practice. There are two reasons for this. First, governments are accountable to all the citizens, and generally cannot afford to implement policies that impose unlimited costs on the non-poor. Secondly, even if society were to agree that such a weighting system was appropriate in theory, the difficulty and controversy surrounding the estimation of poverty lines in practice means that a 'sliding-scale' weighting system would be preferable to a 0–1 system.

4. Alternatives to CBA:

Resource and informational constraints mean that full cost-benefit analysis cannot always be carried out. This means that there is a need for researchers to continue developing, refining and disseminating less information-intensive alternatives. Such approaches should come with an assessment of the likely magnitudes of error which they may be subjected to:

A good example of this practice is van de Walle and Gunewardena (2001), who compared the net benefits from irrigation investments in Vietnam calculated by 'quick and dirty' methods with those calculated by 'slow and clean' methods. The 'slow and clean' method involves estimating, using household survey data and econometric techniques, the effect of the amount of irrigated and non-irrigated land on households' net crop incomes. The method controls various other influences on crop income, and allows the marginal benefits of irrigated land to differ according to district, type of household, and initial level of irrigated land to non-irrigated land.

The 'quick and dirty' method, by contrast, involves simply calculating the difference between the average crop income of farmers using irrigated land and those using non-irrigated land, and interpreting the difference as the marginal benefit of irrigated land. The authors' calculations showed that, if the cost of irrigation investments is low, both methods imply that benefits exceed costs. If, however, the cost of irrigation investments is high, the use of the 'quick and dirty' method can impose substantial costs, if non-beneficial projects are accepted, and beneficial projects are not accepted. The author concluded that, at least in this case, the additional costs of data collection and analysis required for the 'slow and clean method' are justified. However, in their review of actual World Bank appraisal reports for irrigation investments, they found few evaluations which used anything corresponding to such a method.

VII-CONCLUSION

This study has analyzed the likely macroeconomic effects of changes in public investment. In economic literature, strong relation exists for governments in developing countries to implement considerable public investment in raising the economic growth and development. Empirical evidence concludes that the link between public investment and economic development is positive and significant in long run. Since there is more evidence that public capital is productive, it may be even more productive if associated with increasing FDI. But, public investment shows strong contribution to the improvement of human development index as well. Furthermore, public investment in general does not reduce inequality significantly; however, the public investments in health and education sectors do possess immense potentiality in inequality reduction. Another important implication that follows from this study is that public investment is supportive to development only if the public investment is raising overall growth in an economy. It has implication, public investment should be supportive to private investment to raise the overall growth or there should be proper selection of the public sector projects that have high growth potentials. Therefore, project appraisal is necessary to select high growth public sector projects; social cost-benefit approach is instrumental in this regard.

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